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Khufu's pyramid, the speed of light, and the royal cubit, compared

Ian Douglas

ian@zti.co.za

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8452-7111>

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Abstract

There is a claim that the difference in metres between the circumcircle around, and the incircle within the great pyramid, closely mirrors the speed of light, when scaled by powers of ten. The accuracy of this claim depends on the value of the cubit in metres, assuming that Khufu's intended base size was 440 cubits square. This paper examines various popular values of the cubit, against the speed of light claim.

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, Great Pyramid, History of Mathematics, History of Science, π .

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1 Introduction

There are two reasonably well-known (at least amongst alternative researchers) theories linking Khufu's pyramid with the speed of light. The first is that its centre lies on the latitude 29.9792° N, echoing the speed of light in metres per second (29.9792×10^7 m/s). Scott Onstott credits this to Web [1]. An article from 2013 [2] claimed the line went through the grand gallery, so possibly the GPS model was re-aligned since then. I was previously a supporter of the idea, but given how Khufu's construction date is being pushed back [3], I'm not sure how well it will remain a valid idea once we factor in continental drift.

The second claim is that the difference in metres between the circumcircle around, and the incircle within Khufu, closely mirrors the speed of light. The earliest source I can find attributes this to Jonathan Langdale [2]. Assuming that Khufu has a base length of 440 \mathbb{G} , the accuracy here depends on the value of the cubit. Multiple researchers have offered different values for the cubit over the years. I evaluate the speed of light claim against these different values, using both "full" and rounded values for π and $\sqrt{2}$ in the calculation.

"The language of Giza is mathematics."

Robert Bauval

"You will believe."

The architects of Giza

2 Symbols and values

Giza is a construction site. Construction is a practical art, so we need to use practical values for certain irrationals.

Symbol	Name	"Full" value	Practical value	Practical % Accuracy
π	Archimedes' constant	3.141592653...	3.1416	99.9998
e	Euler's number	2.718281828...	2.72 or 2.7183	99.9368 or 99.9993
φ	Golden ratio	1.6180339887...	1.618 $\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 = 2.618$	99.9979
$\sqrt{2}$	Root 2	1.414213562...	1.4142	99.9990
P	Petrie inch	2.5399977 cm		

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

I use "cubit" for the Royal cubit (€).

We should remember that we are dealing with a different culture, which may have had a different approach to accuracy and precision, compared to our modern scientific mindset. My Giza analysis suggests they typically worked to 3 or 4 decimal places. This may indicate that they used abacuses or counting tables, or possibly slide rules or logarithms, to calculate. Alternatively, they may just have used four decimals as anything more did not make sense in construction. 0.0001 € is $5.236 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}$, which is about 50 microns, half the smallest distance that can be seen with the naked eye, and approaching the length of a human liver cell.

3 The arena

The battle, as it were, between the values of the cubit will be fought in Figure 1, which shows the top view outline of the great pyramid with a side of 440 € . The red contained incircle has a diameter of 440 € , while the blue surrounding circumcircle has a diameter of $440\sqrt{2} \text{ €}$.

Figure 1: The circumcircle and incircle for Khufu

The circumference of the incircle is $\pi d = 440\pi$.

The circumference of the circumcircle is $\pi D = 440\sqrt{2}\pi$.

The difference between them is

$$440\sqrt{2}\pi - 440\pi = 440\pi(\sqrt{2} - 1)$$

The question is now, what are the values for π and $\sqrt{2}$?

We either use “full” values, in practice about 9 decimals, although modern calculators may work to 17 places internally, or a more pragmatic approach as in Table 1, using 3.1416 for π and 1.4142 for $\sqrt{2}$. I present the results using both approaches.

Using full values, the difference is 572.567725 €, while using rounded values, the difference is 572.550317 €. These values are close. We will convert these cubit values to metres using the different cubit lengths, and then compare those metre values to the speed of light at 299.792458 Mm/s.

Since we know the circles difference, and the speed of light, we can compute the “ideal” cubit values, which comes out at 0.5235930 using “full” values, and 0.5236089 using rounded values.

4 The contenders

I have collected the values for the cubit in Table 2 from published books, or online. I have tried to find the earliest user or proposer for each value, hopefully correctly. Petrie published various values, with 20.62 ± 0.005 P his best determination for the “original” cubit. I have included all three values for comparison. Original values in modern inches or Petrie-era inches were converted to metres by multiplying by 0.0254 or 0.025399977, respectively.

Christopher Bartlett [4] compiled a list of surveys of the great pyramid. Assuming the base was 440 €, I have divided each base metre length by 440 to get the implied cubit value. Howard Vyse's outlier result pushed Bartlett's summary average higher.

Source	Specification	̵ / Metre
Neal [5]		0.5225
Gardiner, Gillings [6]	20.59”	0.522986
Clagett [7]		0.523
Newton [8]	1.717’	0.52334113
Dash 2012 [4]	230.329m	0.523475
Lehner, Lawton–Herald [4]	230.33m	0.5234773
Lauer et al [9]		0.5235
Petrie, Brabin [4]	230.348m	0.5235182
J. R. Skinner [10]	20.612”	0.5235443
Romer [4]	230.35m	0.5235227
Pile, Atiya [4]	230.356m	0.5235364
Dorner [4]	230.36m	0.5235455
Borchardt/Cole [11]		0.52355
Stecchini [4]	230.363m	0.5235523
Dash 2015 [12]	230.3635m	0.52355341
J.H. Cole [4]	230.364m	0.5235545
Tompkins, Markowsky, Livio [4]	230.365m	0.5235568
Payne [Pers. Corr.]	20.6125”	0.5235575
Mario Buildreps [13]		0.52356
Hawass [4]	230.37m	0.5235682
Verner, Smith [4]	230.38m	0.5235909
Ideal	“full π , $\sqrt{2}$ ”	0.52359301
$\pi/6$		0.52359878
Schwaller de Lubicz et al ($\pi/6$ rounded) [9]		0.5236
Ideal	“rounded π , $\sqrt{2}$ ”	0.52360893
Petrie [14]	20.62 – 0.005”	0.52362053
Hersch-Fischler [4]	230.4m	0.5236364
Berriman [15]	20.61552813”	0.52363441
Moyer [16]	20.618”	0.5236972
Sivertsen [17]	20.618”	0.52370182
Petrie [14]	20.62”	0.52374753
Legon (Petrie 6) [18]		0.523748
Legon (Petrie 5) [18]		0.52375
Bartlett summary average [4]	230.478m	0.5238136
Legon [18]		0.52382
Calter [4]	230.5m	0.5238636
Petrie [14]	20.62 + 0.005”	0.52387453
Sokolowski, Wakefield [19]		0.523875
“Scholarly world” [10]		0.5239
Verhardt [20]		0.523905
Berriman [10]	20.6265”	0.5239131
Rutherford [21]	20.6284”	0.52396136
Verhardt [22]		0.52396377
Lepsius [23]		0.525
Smyth [10]	20.7”	0.5257795
Michell/Neal [24]	20.736”	0.5266944
Vyse [4]	232.8m	0.5290909
Neal [25]	20.97251”	0.5327018
Collins [26]		0.5334

Table 2: Various proposed values for the cubit

Jean Philippe Lauer et al includes Eugene Emile Antoniadi and Gilles Dormion.

R.A. Schwaller de Lubicz et al includes Jean Kerisel, Hubert Poulsen, A.E. Berriman, C. Funck-Hellet, Robert Bauval, Niels Bandholm, Robin Spivey, Robert Edward Grant, Quentin Leplat, and myself.

The differences are shown graphically in Figure 2. I plotted (length in cm - 52) \times 10. Even though the majority are very close in the chart, they will be ten times closer at real scale. Many values are separated by less than a tenth of a millimetre, which is difficult to see, and less than a typical monitor’s resolution of 96 DPI, which is about 0.2646 mm.

Figure 2: Graphical comparison of the various cubit lengths.

The differences are small. The lowest four and six highest are outliers.

Metric	Value
Collins – Neal	10.9000 mm
Rutherford – Neal	1.4614 mm
Rutherford – Gardiner, Gillings	0.9754 mm
Rutherford – Dash 2012	0.4864 mm

Table 3: The range of values

One might thus wonder what the fuss is all about. The full Giza site is over 2341m [27] long, and even a small distance of less than half a millimetre becomes a difference of 2 cubits over that distance. This affects various calculations. We also need to evaluate the relationship between the metre and cubit, and these small differences become important.

5 Results

The speed of light as used (299.792458 Mm/s) has only six decimals, so I have rounded the results likewise. Table 4 shows the results of converting the circles difference, calculated with full values of π and $\sqrt{2}$, from cubits to metres, at the different conversion values. The ideal value is highlighted in green, with the three best highlighted in yellow.

Table 5 shows the results of converting the circles difference, computed with 3.1416 and 1.4142, from cubits to metres, at the different conversion values. The ideal value is highlighted in green, with the three best highlighted in yellow.

Source	̵ / Metre	c Value	Accuracy %	Delta from 100%
Neal	0.5225	299.166636	99.791248	0.208752
Gardiner, Gillings 20.59”	0.522986	299.444904	99.884069	0.115931
Clagett	0.523	299.452920	99.886742	0.113258
Newton 1.717’	0.52334113	299.648240	99.951894	0.048106
Dash 2012 230.329m	0.523475	299.724890	99.977462	0.022538
Lehner, Lawton–Herald 230.33m	0.5234773	299.726207	99.977901	0.022099
Lauer et al	0.5235	299.739204	99.982236	0.017764
Petrie, Brabin 230.348m	0.5235182	299.749625	99.985712	0.014288
J. R. Skinner 20.612”	0.5235443	299.764569	99.990697	0.009303
Romer 230.35m	0.5235227	299.752201	99.986572	0.013428
Pile, Atiya 230.356m	0.5235364	299.760046	99.989188	0.010812
Dorner 230.36m	0.5235455	299.765256	99.990926	0.009074
Borchardt/Cole	0.52355	299.767832	99.991786	0.008214
Stecchini 230.363m	0.5235523	299.769149	99.992225	0.007775
Dash 2015 230.3635m	0.52355341	299.769784	99.992437	0.007563
J.H. Cole 230.364m	0.5235545	299.770409	99.992645	0.007355
Tompkins, Markowsky, Livio 230.365m	0.5235568	299.771726	99.993085	0.006915
Payne 20.6125”	0.5235575	299.772127	99.993218	0.006782
Mario Buildreps	0.52356	299.773558	99.993696	0.006304
Hawass 230.37m	0.5235682	299.778253	99.995262	0.004738
Verner, Smith 230.38m	0.5235909	299.791250	99.999597	0.000403
Ideal “full π , $\sqrt{2}$ ”	0.52359301	299.792458	100.000000	0.000000
$\pi/6$	0.52359878	299.795760	100.001101	0.001101
Schwaller de Lubicz et al ($\pi/6$ rounded)	0.5236	299.796461	100.001335	0.001335
Ideal “rounded π , $\sqrt{2}$ ”	0.52360893	299.801573	100.003040	0.003040
Petrie 20.62 – 0.005”	0.52362053	299.808213	100.005255	0.005255
Hersch-Fischler 230.4m	0.5236364	299.817302	100.008287	0.008287
Berriman 20.61552813”	0.52363441	299.816165	100.007908	0.007908
Moyer 20.618”	0.5236972	299.852114	100.019899	0.019899
Sivertsen 20.618”	0.52370182	299.854759	100.020781	0.020781
Petrie 20.62”	0.52374753	299.880929	100.029511	0.029511
Legon (Petrie 6)	0.523748	299.881201	100.029601	0.029601
Legon (Petrie 5)	0.52375	299.882346	100.029983	0.029983
Bartlett summary average 230.478m	0.5238136	299.918761	100.042130	0.042130
Legon	0.52382	299.922426	100.043353	0.043353
Calter 230.5m	0.5238636	299.947390	100.051680	0.051680
Petrie 20.62 + 0.005”	0.52387453	299.953645	100.053766	0.053766
Sokolowski, Wakefield	0.523875	299.953917	100.053857	0.053857
“Scholarly world”	0.5239	299.968231	100.058632	0.058632
Verhardt	0.523905	299.971094	100.059587	0.059587
Berriman 20.6265”	0.5239131	299.975732	100.061134	0.061134
Rutherford 20.6284”	0.52396136	300.003364	100.070351	0.070351
Verhardt	0.52396377	300.004744	100.070811	0.070811
Lepsius	0.525	300.598056	100.268718	0.268718
Smyth 20.7”	0.5257795	301.044372	100.417594	0.417594
Michell/Neal 20.736”	0.5266944	301.568214	100.592329	0.592329
Vyse 232.8m	0.5290909	302.940373	101.050031	1.050031
Neal 20.97251”	0.5327018	305.007858	101.739670	1.739670
Collins	0.5334	305.407625	101.873018	1.873018

Table 4: Comparison using rounded results from full values for π and $\sqrt{2}$

6 Discussion

Most of the cubit values that we have are a result of averaging existing cubit rods, or averaging measurements of buildings or objects. There are several assumptions inherent in this approach:

1. The items measured are all from the same culture.
2. The items measured were exactly made or built, and have remained unchanged since then.
3. Cubit rods were perfectly copied or manufactured, to a defined standard.
4. The samples measured, if not all perfect, were incorrect in a balanced way around the true value.

Source	̵ / Metre	c Value	Accuracy %	Delta from 100%
Neal	0.5225	299.157541	99.788214	0.211786
Gardiner, Gillings 20.59”	0.522986	299.435800	99.881032	0.118968
Clagett	0.523	299.443816	99.883705	0.116295
Newton 1.717’	0.52334113	299.639130	99.948855	0.051145
Dash 2012 230.329m	0.523475	299.715777	99.974422	0.025578
Lehner, Lawton–Herald 230.33m	0.5234773	299.717094	99.974861	0.025139
Lauer et al	0.5235	299.730091	99.979197	0.020803
Petrie, Brabin 230.348m	0.5235182	299.740511	99.982672	0.017328
J. R. Skinner 20.612”	0.5235443	299.755455	99.987657	0.012343
Romer 230.35m	0.5235227	299.743088	99.983532	0.016468
Pile, Atiya 230.356m	0.5235364	299.750932	99.986148	0.013852
Dorner 230.36m	0.5235455	299.756142	99.987886	0.012114
Borchardt/Cole	0.52355	299.758718	99.988746	0.011254
Stecchini 230.363m	0.5235523	299.760035	99.989185	0.010815
Dash 2015 230.3635m	0.52355341	299.760670	99.989397	0.010603
J.H. Cole 230.364m	0.5235545	299.761295	99.989605	0.010395
Tompkins, Markowsky, Livio 230.365m	0.5235568	299.762612	99.990044	0.009956
Payne 20.6125”	0.5235575	299.763013	99.990178	0.009822
Mario Buildreps	0.52356	299.764444	99.990656	0.009344
Hawass 230.37m	0.5235682	299.769139	99.992222	0.007778
Verner, Smith 230.38m	0.5235909	299.782136	99.996557	0.003443
Ideal “full π , $\sqrt{2}$ ”	0.52359301	299.783343	99.996960	0.003040
$\pi/6$	0.52359878	299.786645	99.998061	0.001939
Schwaller de Lubicz et al ($\pi/6$ rounded)	0.5236	299.787346	99.998295	0.001705
Ideal “rounded π , $\sqrt{2}$ ”	0.52360893	299.792458	100.000000	0.000000
Petrie 20.62 – 0.005”	0.52362053	299.799098	100.002215	0.002215
Hersch-Fischler 230.4m	0.5236364	299.808187	100.005247	0.005247
Berriman 20.61552813”	0.52363441	299.807050	100.004867	0.004867
Moyer 20.618”	0.5236972	299.842998	100.016858	0.016858
Sivertsen 20.618”	0.52370182	299.845642	100.017740	0.017740
Petrie 20.62”	0.52374753	299.871812	100.026470	0.026470
Legon (Petrie 6)	0.523748	299.872083	100.026560	0.026560
Legon (Petrie 5)	0.52375	299.873229	100.026942	0.026942
Bartlett summary average 230.478m	0.5238136	299.909643	100.039089	0.039089
Legon	0.52382	299.913307	100.040311	0.040311
Calter 230.5m	0.5238636	299.938270	100.048638	0.048638
Petrie 20.62 + 0.005”	0.52387453	299.944526	100.050724	0.050724
Sokolowski, Wakefield	0.523875	299.944797	100.050815	0.050815
“Scholarly world”	0.5239	299.959111	100.055589	0.055589
Verhardt	0.523905	299.961974	100.056544	0.056544
Berriman 20.6265”	0.5239131	299.966611	100.058091	0.058091
Rutherford 20.6284”	0.52396136	299.994243	100.067308	0.067308
Verhardt	0.52396377	299.995623	100.067768	0.067768
Lepsius	0.525	300.588916	100.265670	0.265670
Smyth 20.7”	0.5257795	301.035219	100.414541	0.414541
Michell/Neal 20.736”	0.5266944	301.559046	100.589270	0.589270
Vyse 232.8m	0.5290909	302.931163	101.046959	1.046959
Neal 20.97251”	0.5327018	304.998584	101.736577	1.736577
Collins	0.5334	305.398339	101.869921	1.869921

Table 5: Comparison using rounded results from rounded values for π and $\sqrt{2}$

5. The materials used, for example to make cubit rods, were stable over millennia.

Clearly items 2 to 5 can not be taken for granted, but deriving cubit values by averaging a set of measurements assumes that they are. So the starting assumptions in the methodology are fatally flawed. Lepsius analysed about a dozen cubit rods [23], but for various reasons only concentrated on two. The rods were not from the old kingdom, but much newer. The oldest was more than 1000 years after the currently-accepted date for the great pyramid [28]. A review of his work by J.R. Smith [29] raised the same objections to methodology as above, yet it is still the approach used in academia.

The Romans went through three different versions of their foot [30], and there were dozens of variants of the foot in Europe [31], yet somehow we expect the cubit to be sacrosanct and unchanging. From my

point of view, I am only interested in the “original” cubit that was used to build Giza, later variants are irrelevant. So trying to get a value by averaging rods or buildings separated by thousands of years, and subjected to the effects of erosion and abuse, makes little sense.

Even the “politics of science” and religion comes into play. Petrie, for example, uses the curious phrase, “so that it is hardly justifiable to adopt a larger result than $20.620 \pm .005$.” This implies that the “settled science” of his time had a larger value, and Petrie felt pressured to come up with a similar value, but his measurements led him lower, and he quoted the lowest he thought he could get away with.

The elephant in the corner is point 1: Discussions of the cubit are limited to the dynastic Egyptians. This approach may be short-sighted.

Calibrated carbon-14 dating of mortar from the great pyramid has returned dates spanning centuries before the currently accepted reign of Khufu [3]. My own research [27] suggests a construction date many millennia before dynastic Egypt, which of necessity would have been a totally different culture. The Egyptian priests told Solon that their country was ancient [32], and that they had inherited much from a culture that was there before them. Given that the dynastics had no concept of π or φ [33], yet both are evidenced all over Giza [27], and spelled out in decimal digits on the king's chamber walls [34], it is clear that the dynastics did not build Giza. Thus Giza, and with it the cubit, must date from an earlier culture. Combining measurements from that earlier culture, with items from the dynastic eras, is mixing apples with pears and can not give sane results.

As shown in the results, both $\pi/6$ and its rounded version, 0.5236, perform the best in this exercise. The Verner and Smith value is from their base size of 230.38m, which is almost identical to $440 \times \pi/6$, or 230.3834613. In the rounded calculation, Petrie's lower bound is third best.

The question now is, is this a valid way of determining the value of the cubit, or just a coincidence? If it is a coincidence then it is indeed a remarkable one. If it is not a coincidence, then we need to rethink our historical timeline.

This calculation only works with a square of 440 cubits. The Giza builders may have had other reasons for using 440 € for the largest pyramid. The dimension is part of a unified design that produces multiple interesting mathematical relationships [27], so adding links to the speed of light may have been just another demonstration of their skill.

The problem with $\pi/6$, or its rounded version, 0.5236, is where it comes from. The length is one sixth of the circumference of a circle with a one metre diameter, as shown in Figure 3. This means that not only are we relating a pyramid dimensioned in cubits to the speed of light in metres per second, but also relating the cubit directly to the metre.

Figure 3: The origin of $\pi/6$

The 0.5236 value also features in the following equalities, correct to 4 decimals, which feature combinations of π , φ , e , 5, 6, and 7. Here, π is 3.1416, φ is 1.618, φ^2 is 2.618, and e is 2.7183, and all are lengths in metres.

$$\pi - \varphi^2 = \frac{\varphi^2}{5} = \frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\varphi^2 + \pi}{5 + 6} = \frac{2\pi - \varphi^2}{7} = \frac{5\varphi e}{6 \cdot 7} = \frac{7\varphi\pi}{5^2 e} = \left(\frac{\varphi + 1}{e - 1} - 1 \right) = \left(\frac{\pi + 1}{e} - 1 \right) = \mathbb{C}$$

However, this observation leads the researcher in directions that are anathema to historians, because it clearly points to an earlier civilization that developed along similar lines to ourselves, including base-10

mathematics and at least metric units of length. If the speed of light calculation is not pure chance, then they also had the second as a unit of time, and the technology to accurately measure the speed of light.

My recent analysis of the blocks on the King's Chamber floor in the great pyramid [35] picked up two references to the speed of light squared, one in cubits and one in metres. This can not be the 4th dynasty as we know it.

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